

Further Studies on *Salvia Coccinea* Linn

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IN a previous communication¹, we reported the isolation of a minor triterpene, m. p. 210-12° from the petroleum ether (60-80°) extract of *Salvia coccinea* Linn. (Fam: Labiate). On further investigation in petroleum ether (60-80°) extract of *S. coccinea* Linn, yields another triterpene-B (0.005%), m.p. 232-34° along with triterpene-A m.p. 210-12°. The triterpene-A crystallises from benzene-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 210-12°, the elemental analysis of which indicates the molecular formula, C₃₀H₄₈O₂ (M⁺, 440). It imparts yellow colour with tetranitromethane and responds positive to Libermann-Burchardt test for triterpene. Its IR spectrum showed bands at $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3390 (broad, hydroxyl), 1649 (unsaturation) and 885 cm⁻¹ (exocyclic methylene).

That the triterpene-A contains an exocyclic methylene is evident from the NMR spectrum (a doublet of two protons in the regions 4.55 and 4.76 δ) and also from the ozonolysis of the acetate of triterpene which affords formaldehyde, characterized as its dinitrophenylhydrazone.

The NMR spectrum of the triterpene-A in addition to the presence of an exocyclic methylene also shows peaks at δ 0.75-1.60 (methyl and methylene protons), around 3.52 δ (dd, 2H, J=10 Hz, -CH₂OH) and a broad multiplet for one proton centered at 5.15 δ for a vinylic proton. The mass fragmentation pattern of the compound is typical of Δ^{12} -ursene type of triterpene². The mass spectrum of the triterpene-A exhibits peaks at m/e 440 (M⁺), 409 (M⁺-CH₂OH) 232 (retro Diels-Alder fragmentation), 207 (M⁺-232 H), 201 (232-CH₂OH), 189 (double hydrogen transfer from retro Diels-Alder fragment to form a highly conjugated allylic cation or 207-H₂O) and a peak at m/e 133 (201-C₈H₈).

In conformity with the Δ^{12} -ursene skeleton, triterpene-A acetate on catalytic hydrogenation in glacial acetic acid with Adams catalyst afforded a product which on repeated chromatographies gave uvaol diacetate^{3,4}, m.p. 156-158° as one of the products. This diacetate on hydrolysis with 6% ethanolic KOH, furnished a compound, C₃₀H₅₀O₂ (M⁺ 442), m.p. 230-32° identified as uvaol^{3,4} (II) by m.m.p. determination, Co-I. R. and Co-T. L. C. with the authentic specimen of uvaol.

All the above data show that the triterpene-A is dehydrouvaol (I), the location of exocyclic methylene at C₂₀ is being ascertained from the pronounced loss of 68 mass units (C₈H₈) from the fragment ion at m/e 201, giving rise to an intense peak at m/e 133

in the mass spectrum because the presence of exocyclic methylene at C₂₀ presumably facilitates the double allylic cleavage² in the ring E.

Triterpene-B, m.p. 232-34° was found to have molecular formula, C₃₀H₅₀O₂ (M⁺ 442). Its mass spectrum exhibits peaks at m/e 411, 234, 207, 203, 189 besides the molecular ion peak at m/e 442. It forms a diacetate, m.p. 156-58° and was found to be identical with dihydro derivative of triterpene-A [M uvaol (II)] by m.m.p. determination, Co-T.L.C. and Co-I.R. with authentic sample of uvaol.

The chloroform and alcoholic extracts of *Salvia coccinea* on chromatography over Brockmann alumina in the usual way afforded only β -sitosterol.

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Coumarins from the umbels of *Prangos pabularia* Lind

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PRANGOS pabularia Lindl. (Umbelliferae) is very rich in coumarins¹. The roots and fruits are reported for their medicinal value¹. The plant grows

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abundantly in Kashmir (6,000-10,000 ft.)². Isolation of fourteen coumarins *viz.* osthol, oxypeucedanin, peucedanin, aviprin (oxypeucedanin hydrate), prangin, prangenidin, imperatorin, alloimperatorin, komalin, prangolarin, pabularinone, pabulenol and iso-oxypeucedanin from the roots has been reported⁵⁻⁷. Gupta *et al*⁶ reported the isolation of five coumarins, *viz.* osthol, isoimperatorin, imperatorin, bergapten and heraclenin from the umbels.

A check TLC of the petroleum ether extract of the umbels in the course of some routine isolation work [revealed the presence of at least fifteen coumarins. This prompted us to reinvestigate the umbels for coumarins as a result of which seven more coumarins, *viz.* isopimpinellin, xanthotoxin, oxypeucedanin, heraclenol, suberosin, 8-(3-chloro-2-hydroxy-3-methylbutanoxy)-psoralen(I) and oxypeucedanin hydrate have been isolated from the umbels of this plant in addition to those already reported.

The air-dried and powdered umbels were soxhletted with petroleum ether (60-80°) and benzene. The petroleum ether extract on removal of the solvent yielded a residue which was chromatographed over neutral alumina (Grade I). Petroleum ether eluted an oil. Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1) yielded successively isoimperatorin, osthol and suberosin, m.p. 87-88°. Petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluted successively imperatorin, bergapten, xanthotoxin, m.p. 143-44°, and isopimpinellin m.p. 149-50°. Benzene eluates afforded oxypeucedanin, m.p. 142-143° and heraclenin. The benzene-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) elute yielded a residue which on crystallisation from ethyl acetate-*n*-hexane afforded (I) as granular crystals, m.p. 115-16°. The PMR (CDCl₃) spectrum of (I) shows up fifteen protons (odd number of protons) which suggests the presence of chlorine or nitrogen in the molecule. Elemental detection indicated the presence of chlorine. NMR δ : 1.70 (6H, *s* 2 CH₃), 3.10 (1H, *s*, exchangeable with D₂O, OH), 4.11 (1H, *q*, one of-O-CH₂), 4.47 (1H, *q*, -CH (OH)-), 4.89 (1H, *q*, one of-O-CH₂-), 6.36 (1H, *d*, *J* 10 Hz, H-3), 6.83 (1H, *d*, *J* 2 Hz, H-3'), 7.38 (1H, *s*, H-5), 7.68

(1H, *d*, *J* 2 Hz, H-2') and 7.72 (1H, *d*, *J* 10 Hz, H-4). The structure (I) of the compound was established by its synthesis from heraclenin by heating it in methanolic HCl.

Compound (I) has been isolated in 0.06 per cent yield. Its structure strongly suggests that it is an artefact, obviously derived from heraclenin. The compound would be formed by the action of HCl on heraclenin, as has been found to be the case. However, a petrol extract of the umbels is found to contain compound (I) (on TLC) and its isolation does not involve the use of any chlorinated hydrocarbons, a potential supplier of HCl. Therefore, it cannot be said that the compound (I) is an artefact, its formation having taken place in the plant itself.

The benzene extract on chromatography over neutral alumina afforded heraclenol, m.p. 116-17° and oxypeucedanin hydrate, m.p. 129-30°.

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